

A novel textile reinforced concrete U-drain incorporated with waste fishing nets

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In this work, the first-of-its-kind U-drain made of Textile-Reinforced Concrete (TRC) reinforced with waste fishing nets is discussed. Utilizing waste fishing nets allows a new way to employ waste materials in construction products. The investigations employed an anchovy waste fishing net made of nylon with a 5mm aperture. To fortify the TRC U-drain, glass textiles, and waste fishing nets were integrated and coated with an additional layer of epoxy. The characterization of TRC, the flexural performance of TRC panels, and the macro-structural response along with cracking and failure pattern of TRC U-drain under flexural load are reported. Characterization studies showed that integrating waste fishing nets with conventional glass textiles improved their strength and stiffness. It was also observed that the utilization of the waste fishing net enables the optimization of textile reinforcement requirements in TRC. The results of the study also show how waste fishing nets can be utilized as reinforcement in TRC as a sustainable substitute for conventional textile reinforcement. Lastly, the TRC U-drain's load capacity shows that it can be used for stormwater infrastructure, which can lead to a lot of opportunities for a new sustainable product in the construction industry.

KEYWORDS: U-drain; waste fishing net; glass textile; uniaxial tension; flexural performance; textile reinforced concrete.

Ocean plastic pollution is a well-known environmental issue that has an adverse impact on economics, ecology, and aesthetics. Lost, abandoned, and discarded waste fishing nets are estimated to be the primary sources of marine plastic pollution¹. The marine food chain is impacted by these plastic wastes when they break down into microscopic plastic particles. Previously, natural fibers were used to make fishing nets. But as synthetic fibers have advanced, these natural fibers have been supplanted by synthetic fibers². A safe and healthy marine ecosystem should be maintained by avoiding the disposal of waste fishing nets into water bodies. If these nets are piled up in landfills, they may still harm the ecosystem even after they are transported to land³.

To get over these disposal issues, waste fishing nets can be used to reinforce cementitious composites for both structural and non-structural applications⁴. Previous research has suggested using discretized

fishing net waste into short fibers as a concrete reinforcement material⁵⁻⁷. The mechanical and physical characteristics of cement-based materials have been greatly enhanced by the addition of reinforcing fibers. Numerous studies have thoroughly examined recycled waste fishing nets as short-fiber reinforcement in cementitious composites^{2,8-14}, and improvements in flexural behavior have been documented^{2,10}. Waste fishing nets made of polyethylene were utilized in a different investigation as continuous reinforcement in a cement matrix⁹. Furthermore, fishing net lines are made of twisted or braided fibers, thus further processing is not necessary beyond just cutting the nets to the proper length. When polyethylene fibers from used fishing nets were used separately, the post-crack load increased and the peak strength at which the first fracture occurred decreased¹⁵.

With the advent of composite materials such as